

Coverage improvements for sub-Terahertz systems under shadowing conditions

Werner Mohr
Consultant

49th WWRF meeting, March 28 to 30, 2023, Poznan, Poland

mohr_werner@t-online.de

[10.5281/zenodo.14188902](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.14188902)

Outline

- ▶ Introduction
- ▶ Pathloss in sub-Terahertz frequency range
- ▶ Shadowing conditions and channel impulse response
- ▶ Wideband multipath radio channel by strong component
 - ▶ Coherence bandwidth of Rayleigh channel
 - ▶ Coherence bandwidth of Rice channel
- ▶ Technical means to provide quasi LOS conditions
 - ▶ Metallic mirror or reflector
 - ▶ RIS array
 - ▶ Repeater
- ▶ Comparison of different technical means
- ▶ Conclusion

Introduction

- ▶ In 5G and 6G systems frequency bands above 20 GHz and in 6G up to the sub-Terahertz domain are considered
- ▶ Such systems are intended to use wide carrier bandwidth in the order of several hundred MHz to several GHz
- ▶ Radio channel has significant impact on system performance and is characterized by
 - ▶ distant dependent pathloss
 - ▶ multipath propagation
 - ▶ especially shadowing
 - ▶ atmospheric, rain and foliage attenuationwhich results in a statistical description of the channel
- ▶ In WWRF 47th meeting in Bristol it was shown that constructive superposition of different multipath components results in narrowband radio channel
- ▶ How to improve coverage under shadowing conditions and enable wideband radio channel transfer function?

Pathloss contributions: Friis LOS formula, atmospheric and rain attenuation versus r and f

- Atmospheric attenuation for higher vapor density (15 g/m^3)

- For longer range r and higher frequency f atmospheric attenuation is dominating contribution

Source: Mohr, W.: Range and capacity considerations for Terahertz-Systems for 6G mobile and wireless communication. Journal of Mobile Multimedia, Vol. 19, Issue 1, 2022, pp. 215, published September 20, 2022, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.13052/jmm1550-4646.19111>, citation link: <https://journals.riverpublishers.com/index.php/JMM/article/view/18511>. (Range and Capacity Considerations for Terahertz-Systems for 6G Mobile and Wireless Communication | Journal of Mobile Multimedia (riverpublishers.com)).

Shadowing conditions

Indoor or urban environment

- ▶ Under shadowing conditions direct signal transmission along path R_1 blocked at millimeter wave or sub-Terahertz frequency bands especially in urban and indoor environment
- ▶ At receiver
 - ▶ reflected signals (primary and secondary reflections) received with
 - ▶ significantly lower power (☞ Rayleigh channel)
 - ▶ than unobstructed LOS propagation along path R_1 (☞ Rice channel) would allow
- ▶ Technical means needed to direct signal around obstacles for quasi LOS propagation conditions

General multipath propagation scenario between transmitter and receiver

- Claim: With RIS (Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces), e.g., at reflecting surfaces R_1 to R_i the radio environment can be programmed to improve propagation conditions

General multipath propagation scenario between transmitter and receiver

- ▶ Assumption, RIS elements are independent without mutual influence
- ▶ RIS array can be used for beam forming
 - ▶ either towards receiver to increase received power
 - ▶ or towards different directions to avoid paths with long delays, but may increase interference at other directions

- ▶ R_i
- ▶ i
- ▶ m, n
- ▶ k
- ▶ $h_{tR,i,m,n}$
- ▶ $\tau_{tR,i,m,n}$
- ▶ $h_{Rr,i,m,n,k}$
- ▶ $\tau_{Rr,i,m,n,k}$
- ▶ $h_{tr,i,m,n,k}$
- ▶ $\rho(\text{material}, \phi_i, \phi_r)_{i,m,n,k}$
- ▶ $\Delta\tau_{i,m,n,k}$

RIS element i or big reflector
 number of multipath components or involved RIS arrays, $i = 1, 2, \dots, I$
 number of RIS element with array with $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ and $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$, in case of a big reflector there are no sub-elements and $m = n = 1$
 number of user
 tap amplitude of path between transmitter and RIS array i and RIS element m, n implicitly includes pathloss
 delay of path between transmitter and RIS array i and RIS element m, n
 tap amplitude of path between RIS array i and RIS element m, n and the receiver of user k implicitly includes pathloss
 delay of path between RIS array i and RIS element m, n to receiver of user k
 individual impulse response between transmitter to user k via RIS element m, n in RIS array i
 reflection coefficient of RIS element m, n in RIS array i depending on material and relation between angle ϕ_i of incoming wave and angle ϕ_r of outgoing wave to user k
 additional delay in RIS element m, n in RIS array i to user k

General multipath propagation scenario between transmitter and receiver

- ▶ Impulse response of a **single path** from the transmitter via a RIS element to the receiver

$$h_{tr,i,m,n,k}(t) = h_{tR,i,m,n} \cdot \varrho(\text{material}, \phi_i, \phi_r)_{i,m,n,k} \cdot h_{Rr,i,m,n,k} \cdot \delta(t - \tau_{tR,i,m,n} - \Delta\tau_{i,m,n,k} - \tau_{Rr,i,m,n,k}) \approx h_{r,i} \cdot \delta(t - \tau_i)$$

- ▶ Sum of all contributions via a **RIS array** R_i $h_{tr,i,k}(t)$ is given as

$$h_{tr,i,k}(t) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \{h_{tR,i,m,n} \cdot \varrho(\text{material}, \phi_i, \phi_r)_{i,m,n,k} \cdot h_{Rr,i,m,n,k} \cdot \delta(t - \tau_{tR,i,m,n} - \Delta\tau_{i,m,n,k} - \tau_{Rr,i,m,n,k})\} \approx h_{r,i} \cdot \delta(t - \tau_i)$$

- ▶ **Entire impulse response** $h_{tr,k}(t)$ between transmitter and receiver of user k follows as sum of all I multipath components plus the direct component

$$h_{tr,k}(t) = h_{sd,k} \cdot \delta(t) + \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \{h_{tR,i,m,n} \cdot \varrho(\text{material}, \phi_i, \phi_r)_{i,m,n,k} \cdot h_{Rr,i,m,n,k} \cdot \delta(t - \tau_{tR,i,m,n} - \Delta\tau_{i,m,n,k} - \tau_{Rr,i,m,n,k})\} \approx h_{sd} \cdot \delta(t) + \sum_{i=1}^I h_{r,i} \cdot \delta(t - \tau_i)$$

- ▶ If several RIS arrays involved, at receiver still multipath channel with delays determined by geometry
- ▶ RIS can adjust phase shift per RIS element for beamforming but cannot adjust path delays
- ▶ Path with long delays may be avoided by beams pointing to different directions
- ▶ As shown in WWRF 47th meeting in Bristol constructive superposition of multipath components results in very narrowband transfer function depending on delay spread
- ▶ **Is it really feasible to program the radio environment or what does it mean?**

Conditions for quasi LOS propagation and bandwidth considerations

- ▶ Quasi LOS propagation conditions leads
 - ▶ to strong component in channel impulse response and
 - ▶ thereby in Rice channel instead of Rayleigh channel under shadowing conditions
- ▶ Which Rice factor K is needed for very wideband channel by means of coherence bandwidth as required in some 6G scenarios?
- ▶ Signal model for Rayleigh and Rice channels according to Jakes

Source: Jakes, W.C.: Microwave Mobile Communications. John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1974, pp. 45.

Coherence bandwidth of Rayleigh channels

- ▶ Known result for Rayleigh channel based on envelope cross-correlation function (ensemble average)

$$R_e(\Delta\omega, \Delta t) = \langle r_1 \cdot r_2 \rangle = \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty r_1 \cdot r_2 \cdot p(r_1, r_2) dr_1 dr_2$$

- ▶ and joint probability density function

$$\begin{aligned} p(r_1, r_2) &= \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} p(r_1, r_2, \theta_1, \theta_2) d\theta_1 d\theta_2 = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{r_1 \cdot r_2}{(2\pi)^2 \cdot \mu^2 \cdot (1 - \lambda^2)} \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{r_1^2 + r_2^2 - 2 \cdot r_1 \cdot r_2 \cdot \lambda \cdot \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1 - \varphi)}{2 \cdot \mu \cdot (1 - \lambda^2)}\right] d\theta_1 d\theta_2 \\ &= \frac{r_1 \cdot r_2}{\mu^2 \cdot (1 - \lambda^2)} \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{r_1^2 + r_2^2}{2 \cdot \mu \cdot (1 - \lambda^2)}\right] \cdot I_0\left(\frac{r_1 \cdot r_2}{\mu} \cdot \frac{\lambda}{1 - \lambda^2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

- ▶ In literature [Jakes] coherence bandwidth $\Delta\omega$ defined by covariance

$$\rho_{e,cov}(\Delta\omega, \Delta t) = \frac{\langle r_1 \cdot r_2 \rangle - \langle r_1 \rangle \cdot \langle r_2 \rangle}{\sqrt{(\langle r_1^2 \rangle - \langle r_1 \rangle^2) \cdot (\langle r_2^2 \rangle - \langle r_2 \rangle^2)}} = 0.5$$

- ▶ Approximation in literature provides – after lengthy calculation – coherence bandwidth and coherence time

$$0.5 \approx \frac{J_0^2\left(\omega \cdot \frac{v}{c_0} \cdot \Delta t\right)}{1 + s^2 \cdot \Delta\omega^2} \quad \Delta f = \frac{\Delta\omega}{2 \cdot \pi} \approx \frac{1}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot s} \quad \Delta t \approx \frac{9}{16 \cdot \pi} \cdot \frac{1}{f_m}$$

- ▶ v – mobile speed, c_0 – speed of light, Δt – coherence time, s – delay spread, Δf – coherence bandwidth, f_m – Doppler shift

Source: Jakes, W.C.: Microwave Mobile Communications. John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1974, pp. 45.

Coherence bandwidth of Rayleigh channels

- Covariance (Cov) and normalized cross-correlation function (CCF)

$$\rho_{e,Cov}(\Delta\omega, \Delta t) = \frac{\langle r_1 \cdot r_2 \rangle - \langle r_1 \rangle \cdot \langle r_2 \rangle}{\sqrt{(\langle r_1^2 \rangle - \langle r_1 \rangle^2) \cdot (\langle r_2^2 \rangle - \langle r_2 \rangle^2)}}$$

$$\rho_{e,CCF}(\Delta\omega, \Delta t) = \frac{\langle r_1 \cdot r_2 \rangle}{\sqrt{\langle r_1^2 \rangle \cdot \langle r_2^2 \rangle}}$$

- CCF considers the impact of the mean value like the direct component of Rice channels

- Relation between covariance (Cov) and normalized cross-correlation function (CCF)

- $\rho_{e,Cov}(\Delta\omega) = 0.5$ corresponds to $\rho_{e,CCF}(\Delta\omega) = 0.893$ at $s \cdot \Delta\omega = 0.95$
- $\rho_{e,CCF}(\Delta\omega) = 0.887$ corresponds to $\rho_{e,Cov}(\Delta\omega) = 0.474$ at $s \cdot \Delta\omega = 1.0$

- In the following the first correspondence for $\rho_{e,Cov}(\Delta\omega) = 0.5$ is applied with $\rho_{e,CCF}(\Delta\omega) = 0.893$

Coherence bandwidth or Rice channels

- ▶ Same approach as for Rayleigh channel based on envelope cross-correlation function (ensemble average)

$$R_e(\Delta\omega, \Delta t) = \langle r_1 \cdot r_2 \rangle = \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty r_1 \cdot r_2 \cdot p(r_1, r_2) dr_1 dr_2$$

- ▶ and joint probability density function

$$p(r_1, r_2) = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} p(r_1, r_2, \theta_1, \theta_2) d\theta_1 d\theta_2 = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{r_1 \cdot r_2}{(2\pi)^2 \cdot \mu^2 \cdot (1 - \lambda^2)} \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{r_1^2 + r_2^2 + 2 \cdot |h_s|^2 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\mu_1}{\mu}\right) - 2 \cdot |h_s| \cdot (r_1 \cdot \cos \theta_1 + r_2 \cdot \cos \theta_2)}{2 \cdot \mu \cdot (1 - \lambda^2)} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{2 \cdot \lambda \cdot [r_1 \cdot r_2 \cdot \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1 - \varphi) - |h_s| \cdot r_1 \cdot \cos(\theta_1 + \varphi) - |h_s| \cdot r_2 \cdot \cos(\theta_2 - \varphi)]}{2 \cdot \mu \cdot (1 - \lambda^2)} \right] d\theta_1 d\theta_2$$

- ▶ Due to mathematical complexity the Rice amplitude probability distribution is approximated by Gaussian distribution for Rice factor $K' \gg 1$ by series expansion of modified Bessel function I_0

$$p_r(r \approx x) \cdot \sigma_G = \frac{r}{\sigma_G} \cdot e^{-\frac{r^2 + |h_s|^2}{2 \cdot \sigma_G^2}} \cdot I_0 \left(\frac{r \cdot |h_s|}{\sigma_G^2} \right) \approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{2 \cdot \pi}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(x-r)^2}{2 \cdot \sigma_G^2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2 \cdot \pi}} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2} \cdot \sigma_G} - \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{4}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K'}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1+K') \cdot I_0 \left(\frac{K'}{2} \right) + K' \cdot I_1 \left(\frac{K'}{2} \right) \right\} \right)^2}$$

with

- ▶ mean of Rice distribution $\langle r_1 \rangle = \langle r_2 \rangle = \sigma_G \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{4}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K'}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1 + K') \cdot I_0 \left(\frac{K'}{2} \right) + K' \cdot I_1 \left(\frac{K'}{2} \right) \right\}$
- ▶ quadratic mean $\langle r_1^2 \rangle = \langle r_2^2 \rangle = 2 \cdot \sigma_G^2 \cdot (1 + K')$
- ▶ Rice factor $K' = \frac{|h_s|^2}{2 \cdot \sigma_G^2}$

Source: Lee, W.C.Y.: Mobile Communications Design Fundamentals. Second edition, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1993, p. 27.
Abramowitz, M. and I.S. Stegun: Handbook of mathematical functions. Dover Publications, Inc., New York, 1972, p. 377.
Pätzold, M.: Mobile Fading Channels. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, Chichester, 2002, p. 17.

Comparison of the Rice distribution and the Gaussian approximation

$$p_{r_0}(r_0) \cdot \sigma = \frac{r_0}{\sigma} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{r_0^2}{2 \cdot \sigma^2} + K\right)} \cdot I_0\left(\sqrt{2 \cdot K} \cdot \frac{r_0}{\sigma}\right) \quad r_0 \geq 0$$

Rice distribution

- ▶ For $K \geq 2$ good match by the approximation
- ▶ For $K < 2$ more significant deviation

$$p_r(x) \cdot \sigma_G = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2 \cdot \pi}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(x-r)^2}{2 \cdot \sigma_G^2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2 \cdot \pi}} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2} \cdot \sigma_G} - \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{4}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1+K) \cdot I_0\left(\frac{K}{2}\right) + K \cdot I_1\left(\frac{K}{2}\right) \right\}^2\right)^2}$$

Gaussian approximation

Coherence bandwidth or Rice channels with Gaussian approximation

- ▶ Approximated envelope cross-correlation function (ensemble average)

$$R_e(\Delta\omega, \Delta t) = \langle r_1 \cdot r_2 \rangle = \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty r_1 \cdot r_2 \cdot p(r_1, r_2) dr_1 dr_2 \approx \langle x_1 \cdot x_3 \rangle = \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty x_1 \cdot x_3 \cdot p(x_1, x_3) dx_1 dx_3$$

- ▶ and joint probability density function

$$p(x_1, x_3) = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot \sigma_G^2 \cdot \sqrt{1 - \rho^2}} \cdot \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2 \cdot (1 - \rho^2)} \cdot \left[\frac{x_1^2 - 2 \cdot m_G \cdot x_1 + m_G^2}{\sigma_G^2} - 2 \cdot \rho \cdot \frac{x_1 \cdot x_3 - x_1 \cdot m_G - x_3 \cdot m_G + m_G \cdot m_G}{\sigma_G^2} + \frac{x_3^2 - 2 \cdot m_G x_3 + m_G^2}{\sigma_G^2} \right] \right\}$$

with

- ▶ mean of Gaussian distribution

$$m_G = \sigma \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{4}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K'}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1 + K') \cdot I_0 \left(\frac{K'}{2} \right) + K' \cdot I_1 \left(\frac{K'}{2} \right) \right\}$$

- ▶ correlation coefficient

$$\rho(x_1, x_3) = \frac{\langle x_1 \cdot x_3 \rangle - \langle x_1 \rangle \cdot \langle x_3 \rangle}{\sqrt{(\langle x_1^2 \rangle - \langle x_1 \rangle^2) \cdot (\langle x_3^2 \rangle - \langle x_3 \rangle^2)}} \\ = J_0 \left(\omega \cdot \frac{v}{c_0} \cdot \Delta t \right) \cdot \frac{\cos \left(\left(\omega \cdot \frac{v}{c_0} \cdot \cos \vartheta_0 \right) \cdot \Delta t - \Delta\omega \cdot \tau_s \right) - s \cdot \Delta\omega \cdot \sin \left(\left(\omega \cdot \frac{v}{c_0} \cdot \cos \vartheta_0 \right) \cdot \Delta t - \Delta\omega \cdot \tau_s \right)}{1 + s^2 \cdot \Delta\omega^2}$$

- ▶ delay of the strong component τ_s
- ▶ angle of arrival of strong component ϑ_0

- ▶ Envelope cross-correlation function (ensemble average)

$$R_e(\Delta\omega, \Delta t) = \langle r_1 \cdot r_2 \rangle \approx m_G^2 + \rho \cdot \sigma_G^2 = m_G^2 + \rho \\ = \left[\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K'}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1 + K') \cdot I_0 \left(\frac{K'}{2} \right) + K' \cdot I_1 \left(\frac{K'}{2} \right) \right\} \right]^2 + \sigma^2 \cdot J_0 \left(\omega \cdot \frac{v}{c_0} \cdot \Delta t \right) \cdot \frac{\cos \left(\left(\omega \cdot \frac{v}{c_0} \cdot \cos \vartheta_0 \right) \cdot \Delta t - \Delta\omega \cdot \tau_s \right) - s \cdot \Delta\omega \cdot \sin \left(\left(\omega \cdot \frac{v}{c_0} \cdot \cos \vartheta_0 \right) \cdot \Delta t - \Delta\omega \cdot \tau_s \right)}{1 + s^2 \cdot \Delta\omega^2}$$

Covariance and normalized cross-correlation function

- Covariance (simplified), independent of K'

- $\nu = 0$
- $\vartheta_0 = 0$
- $\tau_s = 0$.

$$\varrho_{e,cov}(\Delta\omega, \Delta t) = \frac{\langle r_1 \cdot r_2 \rangle - \langle r_1 \rangle \cdot \langle r_2 \rangle}{\sqrt{(\langle r_1^2 \rangle - \langle r_1 \rangle^2) \cdot (\langle r_2^2 \rangle - \langle r_2 \rangle^2)}} \approx \frac{1}{1 + s^2 \cdot \Delta\omega^2}$$

- Normalized cross-correlation function (simplified), dependent of K'

- $\nu = 0$
- $\vartheta_0 = 0$
- $\tau_s = 0$.

$$\varrho_{e,CCF}(\Delta\omega, \Delta t) = \frac{\langle r_1 \cdot r_2 \rangle}{\sqrt{\langle r_1^2 \rangle \cdot \langle r_2^2 \rangle}}$$

$$= \frac{\left[\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K'}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1 + K') \cdot I_0\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) + K' \cdot I_1\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) \right\} \right]^2 + \frac{1}{1 + s^2 \cdot \Delta\omega^2}}{1 + \left[\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K'}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1 + K') \cdot I_0\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) + K' \cdot I_1\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) \right\} \right]^2}$$

Coherence bandwidth based on normalized cross-correlation function

- ▶ Numerical evaluation by using the relation $\rho_{e,\text{cov}}(\Delta\omega) = 0.5$ corresponds to $\rho_{e,\text{CCF}}(\Delta\omega) = 0.893$

- ▶ Numerical evaluation of

$$\rho_{e,\text{CCF}}(\Delta\omega) = \frac{\left[\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K'}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1 + K') \cdot I_0\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) + K' \cdot I_1\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) \right\} \right]^2 + \frac{1}{1 + s^2 \cdot \Delta\omega^2}}{1 + \left[\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K'}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1 + K') \cdot I_0\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) + K' \cdot I_1\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) \right\} \right]^2} = 0.893$$

provides coherence bandwidth $\Delta\omega$ versus K'

- ▶ For

$$\rho_{e,\text{CCF}}(\Delta\omega \rightarrow \infty) = \frac{\left[\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K'}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1 + K') \cdot I_0\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) + K' \cdot I_1\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) \right\} \right]^2 + \frac{1}{1 + s^2 \cdot \Delta\omega^2}}{1 + \left[\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{K'}{2}} \cdot \left\{ (1 + K') \cdot I_0\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) + K' \cdot I_1\left(\frac{K'}{2}\right) \right\} \right]^2} = 0.893$$

the limiting case $\Delta\omega \rightarrow \infty$ follows for $K' = 3.63 \hat{=} 5.6$ dB

- ▶ Approximations for $0 \leq K' \leq 3.63$

- ▶ for numerical evaluation $s \cdot \Delta\omega = 0.615 \cdot \left(\frac{3.63}{3.63 - K'} \right)^{0.6263}$

- ▶ including Rayleigh channel $s \cdot \Delta\omega = \left(\frac{3.63}{3.63 - K'} \right)^{0.5250}$

- ▶ For $K > 6$ dB the coherence bandwidth tends to infinity

Options to ensure strong component

Metallic mirror or reflector

► Propagation scenario

- Transmit power limited by radiation limits

$$P_T \cdot G_T = EIRP_T$$

- Reflection coefficient of metallic mirror or reflector

$$\rho_m \cdot e^{-j\Delta\phi} \approx -1$$

► Reflection at metallic surface with high conductance

$$P_R|_{reflector} = |\rho_m \cdot e^{-j\Delta\phi}|^2 \cdot P_T \cdot G_T \cdot G_R \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi R_{2,m}}\right)^2$$

$$\approx EIRP_T \cdot G_R \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi \cdot (R_{2a,m} + R_{2b,m})}\right)^2$$

- Plane wave at reflector is reflected in plane wave again
- Received power depends on sum of partial paths

Options to ensure strong component RIS array

► Propagation scenario

- Transmit power limited by radiation limits

$$P_T \cdot G_T = EIRP_T$$

- Radar cross section σ of RIS element assumed to be a metallic sphere with radius $r = \lambda/4$

$$\sigma = \pi \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda}{4}\right)^2$$

- Minimum spacing of RIS elements $\lambda/2$ between $M \cdot N$ RIS elements

- Scattering at RIS elements with high conductance and optimal RIS gain $M \cdot N$

$$P_R \Big|_{RIS,max} = P_T \cdot \frac{G_T}{4 \cdot \pi \cdot R_{2a,RIS}^2} \cdot (M \cdot N) \cdot (M \cdot N) \cdot \sigma \cdot \frac{G_R \cdot \frac{\lambda^2}{4 \cdot \pi}}{4 \cdot \pi \cdot R_{2b,RIS}^2}$$

$$= EIRP_T \cdot G_R \cdot (M \cdot N)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{4^5} \cdot \frac{1}{\pi^2} \cdot \frac{\lambda^4}{(R_{2a,RIS} \cdot R_{2b,RIS})^2}$$

- Plane wave at RIS elements is scattered as spherical wave per RIS element

- Received power depends on product of partial paths

- Without RIS gain (no appropriate phase adjustment) received power reduced by $M \cdot N$

$$l_x \cdot l_y = (M-1) \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2} \cdot (N-1) \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2} \ll R_{2a,RIS} \text{ and } R_{2b,RIS}$$

Options to ensure strong component Repeater

► Propagation scenario

- Transmit power limited by radiation limits

$$P_T \cdot G_T = EIRP_T$$

- Repeater is amplifying and may even regenerate the received signal before transmitting again

- Advanced antenna concepts (MIMO)

- Signal processing adds delay $x_t = 0; y_t = 0$

- Total transmit power

$$P_{T,total} = N \cdot \frac{P_R}{G_T \cdot G_R} \cdot \left(\frac{4\pi R}{\lambda \cdot N} \right)^2 = \frac{P_{T,BS,single}}{N}$$

- Last hop between repeater and user equipment determines received power or maximum range

$$P_{R,user\ equipment} = EIRP_T \cdot G_{R,user\ equipment} \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi R_{2b,rep}} \right)^2$$

- Lower overall transmit power needed and thereby more environmentally sustainable solution
- Wider range or higher received power and thereby higher capacity feasible

Comparison of different technical means

- ▶ Metallic mirror or reflector

$$P_R|_{reflector} = EIRP_T \cdot G_R \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi \cdot (R_{2a,m} + R_{2b,m})} \right)^2$$

- ▶ RIS array including RIS gain

$$P_R|_{RIS,max} = EIRP_T \cdot G_R \cdot (M \cdot N)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{4^5} \cdot \frac{1}{\pi^2} \cdot \frac{\lambda^4}{(R_{2a,RIS} \cdot R_{2b,RIS})^2}$$

- ▶ RIS array without RIS gain

$$P_R|_{RIS,no\ RIS\ gain} = EIRP_T \cdot G_R \cdot M \cdot N \cdot \frac{1}{4^5} \cdot \frac{1}{\pi^2} \cdot \frac{\lambda^4}{(R_{2a,RIS} \cdot R_{2b,RIS})^2}$$

- ▶ Repeater

$$P_R|_{repeater} = EIRP_T \cdot G_R \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi R_{2b,rep}} \right)^2$$

- ▶ Normalized to the received power for the reflector

$$\frac{P_R|_{RIS,max}}{P_R|_{reflector}} = (M \cdot N)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{4^3} \cdot \frac{\lambda^4}{(R_{2a,RIS} \cdot R_{2b,RIS})^2} \cdot \frac{(R_{2a,m} + R_{2b,m})^2}{\lambda^2}$$

$$\frac{P_R|_{repeater}}{P_R|_{reflector}} = \frac{(R_{2a,m} + R_{2b,m})^2}{R_{2b,rep}^2} = \frac{R_2^2}{R_{2b}^2}$$

Comparison of different technical means

▶ Minimum RIS size for same received power as for reflector

- ▶ Minimum RIS array size with RIS gain is increasing significantly with carrier frequency and overall path length
- ▶ Without RIS gain minimum array size is

$$\log \left(M \cdot N \Big|_{min, no RIS gain} \right) = 2 \cdot \log \left(M \cdot N \Big|_{min} \right)$$

- ▶ In practical cases between both limits

▶ Receiver power for the repeater versus reflector

- ▶ Base station transmitter and repeater have the same $EIRP_T$
- ▶ Repeater solution always provides higher received power or wider range
- ▶ By lower overall transmit power

Comparison of different technical means

Topic	Reflector, metallic mirror	RIS array	Repeater
Mounting	Mounted at buildings, towers or lampposts	Mounted at buildings, towers or lampposts	Mounted at buildings, towers or lampposts
Power supply	No power supply	Power supply needed	Power supply needed
Data connection to the network	No additional data connection	Additional data connection needed make deployment difficult and expensive	No additional data connection
Active/passive device	Passive	Active due to signal processing for beam forming	Active due to amplification and potential signal processing for signal regeneration
Overall transmit power	Transmit power needed to cover full range	Transmit power needed to cover full range	Overall transmit power lower than in other solutions and therefore more sustainable
Beam forming	Plane, concave or convex reflector, some fixed static beam shaping	Beam forming by settings phase shifters of RIS elements RIS gain (similar to antenna gain) by increasing number of RIS elements	Directive and/or MIMO antennas
Update versus receiver location	Not needed, because reflector is covering an area around the receiver	For a specific user location, the radio channel can be influenced or adjusted by RIS settings However, the RIS settings are sensitively dependent on the receiver location depending on the beamwidth and require close update due to receiver movements	Needed, because MIMO antenna concepts exploit different resolvable radio channels
Amplification	No amplification	No amplification	Amplification
Signal regeneration	No	No	RF repeater only: No, for analogue repeater (amplifier) Repeater including signal regeneration: Yes, for repeater including signal processing by means of available information from radio interface
Signal processing	No additional signal processing	Additional centralized signal processing between the user equipment, the base station and the RIS, e.g., in base station for optimal RIS settings beyond the radio interface	No additional signal processing beyond the needs of the radio interface (e.g., channel estimation)
Latency	No latency added to signal propagation	No latency added to signal propagation	RF repeater only: Nearly no latency added to signal propagation Repeater including signal regeneration: Signal processing for signal regeneration and antenna algorithms is adding latency to signal propagation
Shadowing mitigation	Yes, allows to look around corners	Yes, allows to look around corners	Yes, allows to look around corners
Coverage improvement	Yes, shaded areas can be covered even in millimeter wave and sub-Terahertz domain	Yes, shaded areas can be covered even in millimeter wave and sub-Terahertz domain	Yes, shaded areas can be covered even in millimeter wave and sub-Terahertz domain

Comparison of different technical means

Topic	Reflector, metallic mirror	RIS array	Repeater
LOS like propagation conditions	Propagation corresponds to LOS propagation	Propagation corresponds to LOS propagation between base station and RIS array and a second LOS propagation between RIS array and user equipment	Propagation corresponds to LOS propagation between base station and RIS array and a second LOS propagation between RIS array and user equipment
Range extension compared to propagation under shadowing conditions	Yes, based on LOS propagation around corners	Yes, based on LOS propagation around corners, only for huge number of RIS elements better than reflector	Yes, based on amplification and directive antennas in repeater and LOS propagation around corners provides in maximum twice the range as for repeater
Strong component in channel impulse response	Yes, reflector ensures stronger component compared to other secondary reflections around user equipment	Yes, reflector ensures stronger component compared to other secondary reflections around user equipment	Yes, reflector ensures stronger component compared to other secondary reflections around user equipment
Type of radio channel at receiver	Rice channel due to strong component Without reflector received power much lower and radio channel corresponds to Rayleigh channel	Rice channel due to strong component Without RIS array received power much lower and radio channel corresponds to Rayleigh channel	Rice channel due to strong component Without repeater received power much lower and radio channel corresponds to Rayleigh channel
Delay spread at receiver	Delay spread generated via secondary reflections around the receiver or other reflecting obstacles with smaller reflection coefficient in the deployment area Rice channel: low delay spread Rayleigh channel: higher delay spread	Delay spread generated via secondary reflections around the receiver or other reflecting obstacles with smaller reflection coefficient in the deployment area Rice channel: low delay spread Rayleigh channel: higher delay spread	Delay spread generated via secondary reflections around the receiver or other reflecting obstacles with smaller reflection coefficient in the deployment area Rice channel: low delay spread Rayleigh channel: higher delay spread
Coherence bandwidth	Enforced Rice channel at receiver provides very high coherence bandwidth (c.f. Section 7.3.3)	Enforced Rice channel at receiver provides very high coherence bandwidth (c.f. Section 7.3.3)	Enforced Rice channel at receiver provides very high coherence bandwidth (c.f. Section 7.3.3)
Inter-symbol interference	With high coherence bandwidth little inter-symbol interference, which reduces equalization effort	With high coherence bandwidth little inter-symbol interference, which reduces equalization effort	With high coherence bandwidth little inter-symbol interference, which reduces equalization effort
Coherence time	With increasing K factor or Rice channel coherence time is increasing Reduced requirements on update rate of, e.g., channel estimation	With increasing K factor or Rice channel coherence time is increasing Reduced requirements on update rate of, e.g., channel estimation	With increasing K factor or Rice channel coherence time is increasing Reduced requirements on update rate of, e.g., channel estimation
Flexibility	Static, no flexibility	Some beam forming due to RIS settings	Very flexible by advanced antenna concepts (MIMO) and signal regeneration
Overall complexity	Low complexity	High complexity	Medium complexity

- Advantage
- No major difference to other concepts
- Disadvantage
- Major disadvantage

Conclusion

- ▶ Recommendations
 - ▶ Shadowing needs to be avoided by appropriate deployment of base stations
 - ▶ Technical means needed to enforce strong component at receiver (Rice channel) and to guide waves around corners
 - ▶ Metallic mirror or reflector
 - ▶ RIS array
 - ▶ Repeater
- ▶ Advantages of Rice channels
 - ▶ Significantly increased coherence bandwidth
 - ▶ Reduced effective intersymbol-interference (more open eye-diagram)
 - ▶ Avoids need for complex time-domain equalization for very wideband, high throughput systems
- ▶ Repeater is overall best solution with medium complexity
 - ▶ Same electronics as for base station / user equipment can be used
 - ▶ Only power supply needed
 - ▶ No additional data connection required as for RIS array
- ▶ Metallic mirror or reflector is cheap alternative with low complexity
 - ▶ No electronics
 - ▶ No power supply and no data connection needed
- ▶ RIS array requires huge number of RIS elements and results in high complexity for RIS signal processing and deployment
 - ▶ Power supply needed
 - ▶ Data connection to centralized signal processing for optimum RIS settings required
 - ▶ RIS settings sensitive to user location and movements